

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CLUSTER APPROACH IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article reflects the opinions about the importance of the cluster approach in modern science. In addition, it pays theoretical attention to the history of the cluster approach and, on the basis of this, recommends the use of this approach to increase the interest of schoolchildren in handicrafts and national handicrafts, and to develop interest competencies.*

Keywords: *modern education, cluster approach, educational infrastructure, educational content, craft, cooperation.*

Education has always been considered an important component of state activity, a constant value, because it is considered the basis of economic development of society, one of the factors of social stability, a source of increasing intellectual, spiritual and moral potential, including the spiritual potential of the population. At the moment, the population's need for education is increasing, and the number of applicants for higher, special, vocational education is also growing.

Today, based on the requirements of the state education standard of the republic, we are witnessing that the slogan of lifelong education is becoming more relevant. In response to this, it should be emphasized that the branching of the network of various types of educational institutions is increasing, the connections between them are becoming stronger and more complex; the attention to educational infrastructure - management forms, development of methodological and research services; strengthening of personnel base, updating of educational content and methods; the personal needs and opportunities of the students is being strengthened.

It can be observed that any country in the world strives to create an education system that allows students to be in demand both at home and abroad after graduation. Therefore, with regard to the educational system, the main task of the state is to perform functions that are not available to other participants of the educational process, for example, it is important to use other mechanisms of financing, providing tax incentives and stimulating the market of educational services, to train qualified specialists in the most promising areas of knowledge through certificating and licensing for training personnel. In such a situation, the mechanisms of social partnership act as a unique regulator of the opinions and interests of all participants of this process. However, the process of implementing social partnership mechanisms in the field of education is complicated by some negative factors related to the unwillingness of educational organizations to implement. One of the ways out of the current situation can be the use of **a cluster approach**, which implies mutual benefit, continuity, cooperation and mutual participation in achieving the goals of the development of the education sector.

The cluster approach in education allows effective and successful action, taking into account the common priority perspective for all partners, in which it is recommended to coordinate joint educational activities. It is this type of activity that makes it possible to provide more effective assistance to the members of the society participating in the partnership, to take a

rational approach to its use, to ensure recognition of the differences of individuals and organizations that are different from each other. For example, this can be witnessed in the process of organizing and implementing joint cooperation activities in the "school-college-university" system, during the transition to pedagogical and production practices. At this point, it was considered important to speak separately about the cluster in the field of pedagogical education.

A cluster in the field of pedagogical education is a set of regionally localized institutions and organizations that cooperate on the basis of agreements and participate in the implementation of the scientific, educational and innovative goals of training specialists in the field of education.

The cluster development of teacher education is a conceptual approach that implies the use of clusters as the main elements for the development of the system of professional training, retraining and professional development of education specialists.

As a result of the study of the literature on the cluster approach and the systematic analysis of foreign experience on this issue, it was shown that the development of education based on the cluster approach was developed in Europe in the 1990s by M. Porter. It began as an extrapolation of the theory of clusters and cluster development. Over the past 20-30 years, universities in both Europe and the United States have expanded through mergers. As a result of the merger, new subjects are being formed, which will save administrative costs and improve the performance of the national education system in international rankings.

Taking these data into account, it should be said that in the future, using this approach in the educational system of the republic can be effective in the case of a deep understanding of the educational conditions of today's Uzbekistan. On the basis of the cluster approach, it is recommended to use it effectively to increase the interest of schoolchildren in handicrafts, specifically national handicrafts, or to improve the competencies of interest in national handicrafts.

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